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SYNTHESIS AND STUDY OF ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF ALLOYS OF THE SYSTEM $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{100-x} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_x$ DOPED WITH REE OXIDES

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of a study of the electrical and dielectric properties of alloys of the system $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{100-x} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_x$ doped with REE oxides. To increase the compaction and chemical resistance of bismuth borates, rare earth elements (REE) oxides are used. Alloys $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{90} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_{10}$ doped with REE oxides (Gd_2O_3 , Dy_2O_3 and Er_2O_3) were synthesized within 1000-1100°C temperature range. The samples were annealed at 373°C for 200 hours. The interaction in the system $[2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2] + \text{Ln}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3$, Dy_2O_3 , and Er_2O_3) was studied by differential thermal (DTA), X-ray phase (XRD) analyzes, as well as by measuring the density, electrical conductivity and dielectric characteristics (ϵ' , $\text{tg } \delta$). It is assumed that for a number of disordered oxide materials with polar properties - metal oxides and metal - bismuth borates, the temperature dependence of conductivity in a wide temperature range is described by the power law $\sigma = \sigma_0 T^n$, which is associated with multiphonon cluster transitions in disordered oxides of bismuth borates doped with rare earth metals.

Keywords: conductivity, multiphonon transitions, cluster centers, dielectric constant, rare earth elements.

Introduction

Recently, there has been an increasing interest in oxide materials based on Bi_2O_3 , B_2O_3 , GeO_2 (SiO_2), and their compounds doped with various impurities [1-4]. Interest in the study of these materials is associated with the possibility of obtaining materials with interesting physicochemical and physical properties: high values of refractive indices, wide transparency in the visible and infrared ranges, which makes them promising for practical use [5-7].

In [8], the electrical conductivity (σ), dielectric constant (ϵ) and dielectric loss ($\text{tg } \delta$), as well as thermal conductivity (χ) and heat capacity (C_p) of alloys of the system $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{100-x} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_x$ were investigated. It was found that in the system, depending on the ratio of the components, it is possible to obtain alloys with not only semiconducting properties, but also materials that can be used as a frequency converter of laser radiation based on stimulated Raman scattering [9].

To increase the compaction and chemical resistance of bismuth borates, rare earth elements (REE) oxides are used. REE oxides also contribute to a decrease in the dielectric constant $\epsilon < (4-5)$ [10, 11]. Considerable attention is paid to REE oxides [12], including Er_2O_3 [13], Pr_2O_3 [14], Gd_2O_3 [15], Ln_2O_3 [16,17]. It is expected that doping with these oxides can expand the possibility of using bismuth borates in electronics to obtain a high information recording density of $1.1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^2$ [18].

Considering the above, it is of interest to doping the alloys of the $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{100-x} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_x$ system with Gd_2O_3 , Dy_2O_3 , and Er_2O_3 oxides, as well as to study the electrical conductivity (σ), dielectric constant (ϵ), dielectric loss (C_p) in the temperature range 300-600 K.

Experimental part

Alloys $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{90} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_{10}$ doped with REE oxides (Gd_2O_3 , Dy_2O_3 and Er_2O_3) were synthesized in a SNOL muffle furnace within 1000-1100°C temperature range. The melts were poured at room temperature onto a titanium plate. All samples were light brown to brown glassy. The samples were annealed at 373°C for 200 hours.

The interaction in the system $[2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2] + \text{Ln}_2\text{O}_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3$, Dy_2O_3 and Er_2O_3) was studied by differential thermal (DTA), X-ray phase (XRD) analyzes, as well as by measuring the density, electrical conductivity and dielectric characteristics (ϵ' , $\text{tg } \delta$).

Differential thermal analysis was performed on a NETZCHSTA 449F3STA-0836-M derivatograph. X-ray phase analysis was carried out on a D2 Phaser diffractometer (Bruker.)

The density of the alloys was determined by the method of hydrostatic weighing; distilled water was used as the working liquid.

The study of electrical conductivity (σ) and dielectric characteristics (ϵ' , $\text{tg } \delta$) was carried out by a stationary method in the 300-600 K temperature range. The investigated samples had the following compositions: №1 (90mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ -10 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2$); №2(90 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ -9.95 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2$ +0.05 mol% Gd_2O_3); №3(90 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ - 9.95 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2$ + 0.05 mol% Dy_2O_3); №4(90 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ -9.95 mol% $2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2$ +0.05 mol% Er_2O_3). The dimensions of the samples were: thickness $d = 2$ -4mm; width $b = 6$ -8mm and length $L = 16$ -18mm.

Results of measurements

Figure 1 shows the curves of the temperature dependence of the specific electrical conductivity σ (T). The curve has the same character for all alloys and with increasing temperature σ (T) increases, i.e. $d\sigma/dT > 0$. However, impurities of REE oxides on the resistance of the matrix (№1) affect differently: when alloying with Gd_2O_3 oxide (№2) the conductivity decreases (curve 2) in the entire temperature range of 300-600 K. Dy_2O_3 impurities (curve 3) have little effect on the conductivity of the matrix (№1). However, at relatively high temperatures ($T > 450$ K) the dependence σ (T) differs from

that for the matrix (№1). Thus, in sample №1 the conductivity changes according to the law $\sigma \sim T^{2.4}$, and in sample №2 according to $\sigma \sim T^{1.5}$. The Er_2O_3 impurity (curve 4) noticeably affects the conductivity σ (T) and changes according to the law $\sigma \sim T^{1.4}$. As can be seen from Fig. 1, the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity can be divided into two parts: $T = 300-385$ K and $T > 450$ K. At $T < 385$ K, the σ (T) dependence is the same for all studied samples and varies according to the law $\sigma \sim T^{0.28}$, i.e. closer to Mott's law [21] and at temperatures above 450 K, the σ (T) grows according to the $\sigma \sim T^n$ law ($n = 2.4-1.4$).

Fig. 1. Temperature dependences of the conductivity of the alloys of the $[(2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3)_{90} - (2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2)_{10} + Ln_2O_3]$ system.

1 – 90mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ – 10mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2$

2 – 90mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ – 9.95mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2$ + 0.05 mol% Gd_2O_3

3 – 90mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ – 9.95mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2$ + 0.05mol% Dy_2O_3

4 – 90mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ – 9.95mol% $2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2$ + 0.05 mol% Er_2O_3

Figure 2 shows the frequency dependences of the conductivity σ (ν). As can be seen from the figure, in the $\nu \leq 10^3$ Hz frequency range, the conductivity of all studied samples does not depend on the field frequency.

At $\nu > 10^3$ Hz, the conductivity σ (ν) of samples № 1,3,4 increases. The most significant change is observed in sample № 3 (Fig. 2, curve 3), doped with 0.05% Dy_2O_3 , and the smallest in sample № 2 (Fig. 2, curve 2).

Fig. 2. Frequency dependences of the electrical conductivity of samples of the $[(2Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3)_{90} - (2Bi_2O_3 \cdot 3GeO_2)_{10} + Ln_2O_3]$ system at $T=305$ K.

●, 1 – $Ln = 0.0$

Δ, 2 – $Ln = Gd_2O_3$

×, 3 – $Ln = Dy_2O_3$

o, 4 – $Ln = Er_2O_3$

Fig. 3. Frequency dependences of the electrical conductivity of the samples of the $[(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{90} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_{10} + \text{Ln}_2\text{O}_3]$ system at 380 K

- , 1 - $\text{Ln} = 0.0$
- Δ, 2 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Gd}_2\text{O}_3$
- ×, 3 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Dy}_2\text{O}_3$
- o, 4 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Er}_2\text{O}_3$

Figure 3 shows the frequency dependence at relatively high temperatures. At $T = 380 \text{ K}$, the frequency

dependence of the conductivity weakens and the weakest change is observed in sample № 4 (Fig. 3, curve 4).

Fig. 4. Temperature dependences of the dielectric constant (ϵ') of alloys $[(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{90} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_{10} + \text{Ln}_2\text{O}_3]$ doped with REE oxides. $\nu = 10 \text{ kHz}$

- , 1 - $\text{Ln} = 0.0$
- Δ, 2 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Gd}_2\text{O}_3$
- ×, 3 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Dy}_2\text{O}_3$
- o, 4 - $\text{Ln} = 0.05\% \text{ Er}_2\text{O}_3$

In fig. 4 shows the temperature dependence of the dielectric constant (ϵ') in the 300-580 K temperature range. It can be seen from the graph that when passing from the matrix (№1) to doped samples, the value of the dielectric constant ϵ' decreases. Sample №4 has the lowest value, in which ϵ' is 30% less than that of the

original $(2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3)_{90} - (2\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{GeO}_2)_{10}$. A slight increase in $\sigma(T)$ is observed in all samples in the 400–460 K temperature range.

Discussion of results

The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of most disordered materials (oxide borates of

bismuth and other oxide materials) has the form of a curve with an activation energy decreasing with decreasing temperature. This fact is usually explained by the presence of several charge transfer mechanisms with different activation energies that dominate at different temperatures. It is assumed that the governing mechanism of charge transfer in this case is the transport of carriers along the level of percolation corresponding to percolation clusters [19, 20]. Our experimental results obey this rule within the margin of error. The experimental results (Fig. 1) showed that $\log\sigma$ is a linear function $10^3/T$ ($\lg\sigma \sim f(\frac{10^3}{T})$), and the hopping conductivity with variable hopping length is proportional to $A_{\text{exp}}(-\frac{\Delta E}{T^{1/4}})$, as a rule, linearity is not observed. However, in the 300-385K temperature range in all samples, including the original (№1), $\sigma(T)$ changes almost linearly according to the law $\sigma \sim T^n$ ($n = 0.26-0.30$), i.e. closer to $T^{1/4}$ according to Mott's law [21]. In the region 385-440 K, passing through a weak extremum, the value of $\sigma(T)$ (Fig. 1) decreases. The decrease in the conductivity in this region is apparently associated with a decrease in the carrier mobility with increasing temperature.

At $T \geq 450\text{K}$, the electrical conductivity increases with increasing temperature at different rates depending on the composition (Fig. 1). A more active increase in electrical conductivity is observed in sample №1 (Fig. 1, curve 1), i.e. when a REE oxide is added to the initial composition, the relative activation energy decreases. Calculations show that the activation energy at $T \geq 450\text{K}$ changes according to the law $\sigma \sim T^n$ ($n = 2.4$ for №1; 1.5 for №2 and 3; 1.4 for №4). That is, the activation energy decreases at the transition $\text{Gd} \rightarrow \text{Dy} \rightarrow \text{Er}$, respectively. In the temperature range of 300-600K, the conductivity increases (ie improves) in the same sequence and the samples become stronger.

The results obtained indicate that the studied compositions have complex physicochemical properties and require further study. Under real experimental conditions, it turns out to be very difficult to distinguish two laws: the well-known Mott law for hopping conductivity with a variable hopping length [20] and the power law $\sigma = \sigma_0 T^n$, which we associate with multiphonon carrier transitions between cluster centers in the studied disordered oxide materials [20-22].

For frequencies $10^1 - 10^3$ Hz, i.e. significantly lower than the frequencies of the IR range, the conductivity of the samples (Figs. 2 and 3), almost does not change ($\sigma \sim \nu 0.4$). As the field frequency increases, the conductivity of the samples increases accordingly. In the frequency range $10^3 \leq \nu \leq 10^6$ Hz in the studied samples, the values of the conductivity $\sigma(\nu)$ change in different ways (Fig. 2, $T = 305\text{K}$). The largest increase in the conductivity $\sigma(\nu)$ is observed in sample №3, where the impurity is Dy_2O_3 (0.05%). For example: at $\nu = 10^5$ Hz, the conductivity value increased for $\frac{\sigma'}{\sigma_0} \approx 1.2$ times, and in the original sample (№1), $\frac{\sigma'}{\sigma_0} \approx 1.05$ times (i.e. 5%). In sample №2 (an Er_2O_3 impurity), an increase in conductivity is observed at high frequencies ($\nu > 10^5$ Hz). Analysis shows that the frequency dependence of the conductivity is approximately consistent with the

temperature dependence of the conductivity. Both results, $\sigma(T)$ and $\sigma(\nu)$, agree with the model of multiphonon carrier transitions between cluster centers in disordered oxide materials.

Figure 3 shows the results of studying the frequency dependence of the conductivity $\sigma(\nu)$ at relatively high temperatures ($T = 380\text{K}$). As you can see, they weaken at $T = 380\text{K}$. At $\nu < 10^3$ Hz, the conductivity is almost independent of frequency, i.e. $\sigma(\nu) = \text{const}$, and at $\nu > 10^3$ Hz, $\frac{d\sigma}{d\nu} > 0$ increases. For sample №3, the value of $\frac{d\sigma}{d\nu}$ is relatively larger and is equal to $\frac{\sigma'}{\sigma_0} \approx 1.1$ ($\sim 10\%$). For the other samples, the change $\frac{d\sigma}{d\nu}$ is insignificant. Apparently, this is due to the fact that as the phase transitions are approached [5, 6], the chaotic dissociation of cluster centers increases and, due to this, the intensity of the anharmonicity of multiphonon transitions increases. As a result, polarization changes, which affects the directional conductivity of disordered oxide materials.

Figure 4 shows the experimental results of the temperature dependence of the dielectric constant (ϵ') in the studied samples. Figure 4 shows that in the 300-400K temperature range, the value of $\epsilon'(T)$ is constant. At $T = 400-460\text{K}$ in the studied samples, the dielectric constant, passing through the extremum, noticeably decreases. However, in samples №2 and №4, no obvious extremum is observed. In the region of these temperatures, passing through a gentle extremum, the dielectric constant decreases. Unlike the original sample (№1) in samples №2, 3, 4 doped with REE oxides, the value of ϵ' decreases in the investigated temperature range ($T = 300-600\text{K}$). The largest decrease in dielectric constant (almost 23%) relative to the original sample №1 is observed in sample №4 (Fig. 4 curves 4), where 0.05% Er_2O_3 was used as an additive. It is noteworthy that we did not take into account in each sample the partial pressure of oxygen and the effect of the oxidation state of cations on the conductivity, i.e. about the acidity of the melt. Taking into account these and other factors, it will be possible to obtain more reliable results

Conclusion

1. It was found that conductivity in the samples arises due to the dissociation of chaotically excited cluster centers. Multiphonon transitions strongly scatter current carriers, reducing the conductivity of oxide disordered materials.

2. In the samples, the conductivity increases significantly as a result of the dissociation of cluster centers (at $T > 400$ K) with the appearance of vacancies.

3. Conductivity is determined by holes and their mobility decreases with increasing temperature.

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MELT FLOW INVESTIGATION OF BUTADIENE NITRILE RUBBER MODIFIED WITH CHLORINATED POLYISOPRENE

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Abstract

Research has been conducted to study the effect of chlorinated polyisoprene on the rheological properties of butadiene-nitrile rubber under the influence of different temperatures and stresses. The volume consumption of alloys of binary mixtures of butadiene-nitrile rubber chlorinated polyisoprene under the conditions of temperature and stress was studied and the appropriate processing mode was determined. According to the analysis of the obtained results, the rheological properties of alloys of SKN-40/ chlorinated polyisoprene mixtures are expedient to process the amount of chlorinated polyisoprene in this binary mixture by taking 4-5 mass parts and at a temperature of 150°C .

Keyword: Butadiene-nitrile rubber, chlorinated polyisoprene, binary compounds, alloy volume consumption, different temperatures and stresses.

Compositions based on butadiene and acrylic nitrile copolymer (Butadiene-nitrile rubber BNR) are used in various sectors of the economy, such as petrochemistry, mechanical engineering, aviation, etc. widely used in industries. In order to improve the structure of butadiene-nitrile rubber and the technical and special properties of the product based on it, it is combined with various structural and natural compounds,

such as fillers, compounds with functional groups - oligomers, monomers, polymers, etc. is added (1). For this purpose, in our research, we obtain double binary mixtures with mechano-chemical modification of butadiene-nitrile rubber (SRN-40) in different proportions with highly dispersed chlorinated polyisoprene (CPI).